

Eco-Product Form Design: A Multiattribute Decision Making Approach

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ABSTRACT

This paper proposes an approach for determining the design combination of product form elements that match a given product image and eco-product value (EPV). The experiments on the perception of product images and perceivable EPV attributes are conducted with office chairs as an example. Fifteen EPV attributes are identified and categorized into aesthetic, functional, and environmental dimensions. An office chair design database based on the neural network (NN) model is built consisting of 960 different combinations of product form elements, together with their associated product image and EPV values. The application of the design decision support database and a multiattribute decision making method provides product designers with the design alternatives for representing specific eco-product design concepts in terms of product images and EPV attributes to an office chair design. As a result, these eco-product form design alternatives provide useful insights in facilitating the office chair design process.

Keywords: eco-product design; neural networks; TOPSIS.

INTRODUCTION

For the increasing public interest in environmental issues, many companies have started designing products with environmental attributes. In the practice of eco-design, life cycle assessment (LCA) methodology provides the basic modeling framework and environmental criteria for evaluating the environmental load and impact through out the entire product life cycle from material acquisition to disposal (Kobayashi, 2006; Vezzoli and Sciama, 2006). It provides decision makers with quantified product or system related information of energy and material streams and reveals initiation related impacts to the ecosystem.

Eco-product marketing barriers may be laid by such reasons as higher price, lower quality, product/brand image, and lower reliability, due to unstable physical/chemical characteristics, and lack of product information, communication, aesthetics, functionality, service, and corporate sustainable social responsibility. The environmental performance facts are of limited interest if the product does not fulfill its basic functions, and hence cannot be successful on the market. In addition, potential consumers are willing to consider the durability of products at the point of purchase (Dobers and Strannegard, 2005; van Nes and Cramer, 2005). The issue of aesthetic consumption in the modern society has been raised since some studies claim that effective manufacturing of products no longer holds a sufficient competitive advantage. Instead, the route to commercial success is supposed to be found in the artful creation of aesthetic offerings, of images and brands (Davies and Elliott, 2006; Horie et al., 2005; Zafarmand et al., 2003; Walker, 1995). A number of methodologies and tools for eco-design of physical products have been developed based on technical and efficiency solutions. However, very few of those methodologies and tools have succeeded in effectively incorporating the needs of consumers. Manufacturers should be more careful of consumers' needs if they pursue profitable activities through sustainable consumption (Karlsson, 2006; Yim and Herrmann, 2003). To do so, the value concept of the product has been suggested among the crucial issues, because value is the interface between consumers and manufacturers. And it is obvious that value is a concept varying from one consumer to another. To address this issue, this study examines consumers' perception for evaluating the relative value of eco-product attributes such as form aesthetics, function, and environmental attributes. Consumer-oriented experiments are applied to the eco-product design development and

enhancements of consumer perception of value attributes.

In subsequent sections, we first extract the experimental eco-product samples, product form elements, product image word pairs, and visually perceivable EPV attributes. Next, a neural network model is developed to generate a design decision support database for predicting the product image and EPV value of a given form design. In addition, different EPV attribute weights are given by product designers and calculated by using the multiattribute decision making (MADM) method. Finally, this study has established the database for value evaluation of eco-product form design for reflecting specific design objectives in terms of the product image and EPV values.

CONCEPT OF ECO-PRODUCT VALUE

The concept of value based on consumers' perception would consist of a wide variety of product attributes and higher level abstractions. Through an exploratory qualitative research such as company interviews, focus group interview, and in-depth consumer interview, Zeithaml (1988) claims that the perceived value is the consumer's overall assessment of the utility of a product based on perceptions of what is perceived and what is given. From the consumer's perspective, price is what is given up or sacrificed to obtain a product, which includes objective price (the actual price of a product), perceived price (the price as encoded by the consumer), and sacrifice (time cost, search cost, effort cost, psychic cost). Moreover, Zeithaml (1988) indicates that price and quality are not specific product attributes but higher level abstractions. The price and quality can be measured objectively. Both price and quality have been embedded explicitly in the consumer perception and are thus not considered in this study.

The term "eco-value" has been defined from the perspectives of economic costs and environmental impacts, which refers specifically to technical evaluation on the market and environment. However, other factors relate to the value creation of eco-products should not be overlooked, such as product aesthetics, functionality, and the consumer's expectations/perceptions.

Masuda (2001) proposes three forms of eco-value: "eco-value of the senses", "eco-value of the mind", and "eco-value of desires" in a recycling-based society. Especially, "eco-value of the mind" explores the aesthetic awareness which corresponds to a lifestyle, e.g. light and simple, aiming for co-existence with the natural environment. It is highly compatible with an ecological sense of values. To examine the relationship between the environment and aesthetics, Tischner (2001) proposes that the lower aesthetic appeal of eco-products is one of the existing obstacles to buying eco-efficient products. This suggests that eco-product design should consider aesthetics. It is important to think about an aesthetic feature that supports long term use (Rams, 2001; Lewis et al., 2001). The continuation of an eco-product's aesthetic appeal during its useful life needs to be considered by eco-product designers in the eco-product design process. In addition, the effects of environment, repair, use and user's physical characteristics can affect the aesthetics of a product. Being aware of the effects on eco-product features by considering its entire lifecycle may help the product designer improve its aesthetic durability. Table 1 shows the studies in relation to "value" and "eco-value". Despite their significant contributions to the eco-value concept, these studies cannot support eco-product designers for specific design decisions since only concepts and their frameworks are proposed. The concept of eco-product value is often intuitive and emotional, and is difficult to quantify as measuring the value of an eco-product has always been a challenging issue. Few studies have been specifically focused on consumers' perception of eco-product design in terms of aesthetics, function, and environmental considerations, all at once. The sustainable development of eco-products aims at reaching a compromise among these three distinctive dimensions, on which their value should be based. For example, the value of an office chair with environmental labels may be manufactured using recycled material, but the functional quality may be inferior to the genesis. Especially, the appearance of eco-products may not look as good as regular ones.

Concept of value	Description	Source
List of values	nine higher level consumer value attributes derived from surveys	Kahle et al. (1986)
Perceived value (value based on consumer's perception)	(a) low price (b) whatever I want in a product (c) the quality I get for the price I pay (d) what I get for what I give (e) price and quality are not specific product attributes (f) consisting of product attributes and higher level abstraction (g) attributes : intrinsic (physical composition of the product) and extrinsic (e.g. price, brand name) cues	Zeithaml (1988)
Three forms of eco-value	(a) sense, mind, and desire (b) conducting design experiments with recycling and reusing materials	Masuda (2001)
Eco-costs / value ratio	perceiving the eco-efficiency of products/services after product sale by environmental experts and non-experts	Vogtlander et al. (2002)
Eco-means-end chain	four levels: attributes, functional space, psychosocial sequences, and value	Yim and Herrmann (2003)
Total economic value	use value and non-use value	The World Bank (2005)
Eco-value analysis (Eco-VA)	analyzing functions of a product from economic costs, consumer's importance and environmental impacts	Kimita et al. (2007)
Value chain	(a) the consumer as the principal driver of value (b) demand chain + supply chain = value chain	Walters and Rainbird (2007)
Eco-value	ratio of life cycle cost / environmental load	Stevens (2009)

Table 1. Concepts of value from various perspectives.

To address this issue, this study proposes a methodological framework for evaluating eco-product value (EPV) with three dimensions which are to be integrated by their associated attributes to represent the value of eco-products. An EPV is a combined value of product aesthetic, functional and environmental dimensions, which are regarded as the factors for evaluating the value of eco-products.

EXTRACTING AND EVALUATING EXPERIMENTAL SAMPLES

In this study, consumer-oriented experiments are conducted to link the consumers' feeling of a product, represented by EPV attributes and product image word pairs, with the product form elements of the product by using Kansei engineering (Nagamachi, 1995).

The product image of consumers' perception is called "Kansei" in Japanese. The term of "Kansei" embraces all subjective issues of product which are concerned with consumer's emotion and needs (Matsubara and Nagamachi, 1997). Consumers' view of product image is usually different from the way that designers look at product elements or characteristics. Consumers may choose a product mainly based on their perception of product image, while product designers and engineers design a

product by considering physical characteristics of the product. As such, we use the process of Kansei engineering to extract experimental samples as numerical data sets required for NN analysis.

EXTRACTING EXPERIMENTAL SAMPLES

The office chair is a general consumer product and exhibits wide variety in product form with various visual structures. In this study, the product of office chairs is selected as eco-product (environment-friendly product) sample, from which part of them may apply environment-friendly technology and be entitled environmental labels such as, LEED (USA), UN-Global Compact, ISO9001/14001, GREENGUARD™, and GECA (Good Environmental Choice, Australia). However, consumers can hardly distinguish general products from eco-products due to complex criteria, such as recycled material, assembly and disassembly, reuse, and waste management. Thus, this study assumes all product samples are eco-products with varying levels of technical and environmental consciousness.

To facilitate the assessment process made by a group of 20 subjects, we perform a cluster analysis on the 100 office chairs based on the result of multidimensional scaling analysis (MDS). With the generation of a cluster tree diagram, we extract 27

Figure 1. Twenty-seven extracted product samples

representative office chair samples, including 22 training samples and 5 test samples for training and testing the NN model to be developed. Figure 1 shows the 27 experimental office chair samples.

MORPHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF PRODUCT FORM ELEMENTS

We first use morphological analysis (Lin et al., 2007) to extract common product form elements of office chairs. One hundred office chairs are collected as the experimental samples. The morphological analysis involves two steps. In the first step, 5 furniture designers with at least 10 years of office chair design experience are asked to write down the influential product form elements of the office chairs that will affect consumers’ perception of office chairs, according to their knowledge and experience.

In the second step, the 5 furniture designers discuss the results through online Skype and combine similar opinions or components. In this study, the product form of office chairs is represented by both the outline shapes and the product elements. The results are grouped into two parts: form feature and form treatment. The form feature part includes the size and shape of outline components making up the office chair, such as Back area, Back shape, Back thickness, Seat thickness, Armrest type, and Base type. The form treatment part indicates the relationship between outline components, e.g. the connection of Back and seat. Each form element has different types of its own, ranging from two to five, as indicated by the type number 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5. As a result of the morphological analysis, Table 2 shows the 7 influential product form elements extracted from the 100 office chairs, together with 20 associated types.

EXTRACTING PRODUCT FORM IMAGE AND EPV ATTRIBUTE OF EXPERIMENTAL SAMPLES

To collect numerical data for modeling and analyzing consumers’ perception on office chairs, 40 subjects are involved in evaluating the degree to which the 27 representative office chair samples match product image word pairs and a given set of EPV attributes.

Product image word pair selection

Basically, pairs of product image words are often

Product Form Elements	Type 1	Type 2	Type 3	Type 4	Type 5
1. Back and seat (X ₁)	Separated (X ₁₁)	Integrated (X ₁₂)			
2. Back area (X ₂)	Large (X ₂₁)	Medium (X ₂₂)	Small (X ₂₃)		
3. Back shape (X ₃)	Square (X ₃₁)	Square with Rounded Corner (X ₃₂)	Trapezoidal (Rounded corner) (X ₃₃)	Round (X ₃₄)	
4. Back thickness (X ₄)	Thick (X ₄₁)	Thin (X ₄₂)			
5. Seat thickness (X ₅)	Thick (X ₅₁)	Thin (X ₅₂)			
6. Armrest type (X ₆)	Loop (with/without support) (X ₆₁)	T-shaped (X ₆₂)	2- point support (back + seat) (X ₆₃)	1-point support (back or seat) (X ₆₄)	None (X ₆₅)
7. Base type (X ₇)	5-wheel (X ₇₁)	4-wheel (X ₇₂)			

Table 2. Product form elements extracted by morphological analysis on office chair samples.

used to describe the consumer's psychological perception about the image of a new product. To extract the representative product image word pairs for describing the consumer's perception of the product image about office chairs, the following steps are carried out:

Step 1: Collect a large set of product image word pairs from magazines and product catalogues. In this study, we collect more than 50 image word pairs. Considering the work load for survey participants, the product image word pair number is reduced to 12 adjective image word pairs as shown in Table 3 and are considered suitable for describing the image of an office chair. These word pairs are first selected by 10 professional office chair designers.

Step 2: Evaluate the collected product image word pairs using the semantic differentials (SD) method.

Step 3: Apply the factor analysis to the result of SD obtained at Step 2.

Step 4: Determine the representative product image word pairs of the product images based on the analyses performed at Step 3.

This study conducts the factor analysis to select product image word pairs using 5 scales (1 to 5) of the semantic differential (SD) method. Consequently, 6 representative product image word pairs are extracted for office chairs including Classic-Modern (C-M), Decorative-Functional (D-F), Angular-Round (A-R), Heavy-Light (H-L), Craft-HiTech (C-H), and Monotonous-Creative (M-C).

Expert interview for extracting EPV attributes

For extracting EPV attributes and from which can be perceived visually, expert interviews are conducted by providing a semi-structured questionnaire. 7 male and 3 female professional product designers with an average of 15 years' design experience are interviewed. Each of them has more than 10 years' professional office chair design experience. The participated expert is asked to review the listed attributes and tick these attributes which can represent for each dimension. Then, the participated

experts try to select attributes which can be perceived visually from the ticked attributes.

To extract EPV attributes for describing the consumer's perception of the EPV attributes about office chairs, the following steps are carried out:

Step 1: Collect a set of EPV attributes from the literature and product designer interviews.

Step 2: Evaluate the collected EPV attributes using the semi-structured questionnaire.

Step 3: Apply the percentage rule (50%) to the result of semi-structured questionnaire survey obtained at Step 2.

Step 4: Determine the representative perceivable EPV attributes as shown in Table 4. Some environmental attributes are more recessive and would be better provided with details for participants to understand. As such, the attribute description is amended based on product designers' opinions in the environment dimension.

Originally, 8 and 4 attributes are from the aesthetic and functional perspectives respectively, while 21 attributes are from the environmental perspective. These attributes are all designated to analyse the value of eco-products. For selecting representative EPV attributes from three perspectives, all aesthetic and functional attributes are selected, while 20 out of 21 environmental attributes are selected.

However, not all of EPV attributes may be perceived directly by consumers due to the unknown information, such as the manufacturing technology and process, technical quality, cost, and energy consumption. As such, the perceivable EPV attributes among all selected EPV attributes are surveyed using the percentage rule (50%) by these product designers simultaneously and the results are shown in Table 4. 7 out of 8 aesthetic attributes as well as 3 out of 4 functional attributes are selected. 5 out of 16 environmental attributes are selected as EPV attributes.

1. Classic-Modern (C-M)	2. Complex-Simple (C-S)	3. Biomorphic-Geometric (B-G)
4. Unsteady-Steady (U-S)	5. Decorative-Functional (D-F)	6. Angular-Rounded (A-R)
7. Heavy-Light (H-L)	8. Unimpressive-Magnificent (U-M)	9. Ordinary-Distinctive (O-D)
10. Craft-HiTech (C-H)	11. Monotonous-Creative (M-C)	12. Soft-Hard (S-H)

Table 3. Twelve product image word pairs for office chairs.

		Eco-Product Value (EPV) attribute
Aesthetics	Y ₁	Harmonious form proportion (8)
	Y ₂	Form Consistency (8)
	Y ₃	Fashionability (6)
	Y ₄	Timeless style (5)
	Y ₅	High cultural identity (8)
	Y ₆	Elegancy (7)
	Y ₇	Form simplicity (9)
Function	Y ₈	Comfortability (6)
	Y ₉	Stability (5)
	Y ₁₀	Ease of mobility (6)
Environment	Y ₁₁	Upgradability & modularity- ease of maintenance, ease of replace, and extending product life (5)
	Y ₁₂	Space adaptability- suitable for various office spaces e.g. large or small size spaces, visitor room, or other public areas (8)
	Y ₁₃	Simplicity & minimalism of mechanism- reducing numbers of components and material (6)
	Y ₁₄	Ease of disassembly- shorter process and using simple tools (5)
	Y ₁₅	Harmony with environment- harmonious relationship between the consumer, product, and environment (7)

Table 4. Fifteen EPV attributes perceived visually with the selection (out of 10) enclosed in parentheses.

EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS WITH NN MODELS

With their effective learning ability, NN models have been widely used to examine the complex and non-linear relationship between input variables and output variables (Nelson and Illingworth, 1991). Neural networks are matching the product form (the input) to the consumers' perception of product image (the output), which is often a black box and cannot be precisely described. With a single hidden layer, the NN model is a multilayered feed-forward one trained with the back-propagation learning algorithm, as it is an effective and popular supervised learning algorithm. The NN model uses the Delta learning rule and the Sigmoid transfer function for all layers (Golden, 1996). All of input and output variables (neurons) are normalized before training. The default settings of the NN software are used, including learning rate, momentum, bias terms and weights.

In this study, we also develop four NN models, called NN1, NN2, NN3, and NN4 respectively, in order to examine how a particular combination of 7 office chair form elements matches 6 product images and 15 eco-product EPV attributes. The 20 types of the 7

product form element in Table 1 are used as the 20 input variables for the NN model. If the office chair has a particular product form element type, the value of the corresponding input neuron is 1; otherwise, the value is 0. The 27 office chair samples in the training set, given in Figure 1, are used to train four NN models. Each model was trained 5,000 epochs at each run. When the cumulative training epochs are over 25,000, the training process was completed.

PRODUCT IMAGE ANALYSIS WITH NN MODELS

The left part of Table 5 shows that the number of neurons in the single hidden layer of NN1 model is 13, which is determined by (the number of input neurons + the number of output neurons) / 2. The number of neurons in other models is 11, 26 and 52, to NN2, NN3 and NN4 based on the corresponding formula respectively. The left part of Table 6 shows the lowest RMS error of the NN model for the test set is 0.1672 within the NN1 model, which performs the highest predictive accuracy rate among four NN models.

EPV ATTRIBUTE ANALYSIS WITH NN MODELS

The right part of Table 5 shows the number of neurons used in the input, hidden and output layers of the NN model. The 20 types of the 7 design element in Table 1 are used as the 20 input variables for the NN model. The number of neurons in the single hidden layer is 18, 17, 35 and 70, to NN1, NN2, NN3 and NN4 based on corresponding formula respectively. The assessed average values of the 15 EPV attributes are used as the output neurons. The lowest RMS error of each NN model is collected. The right part of Table 6 shows the lowest RMS error of the NN model for the test set with 0.0928, which performs the highest predictive accuracy rate for the EPV attribute among four NN models.

EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS WITH TOPSIS

Multiattribute decision making (MADM) is a methodology that aids the decision maker in making preference decisions (e.g. assessment, ranking, and selection) over a finite set of available alternatives characterised by multiple, potentially conflicting attributes (Yoon and Hwang, 1995; Yeh, 2003). It provides a formal framework for modeling

NN model	Input layer:	20 neurons (20 office chair form types)	
	Output layer:	6 neurons (6 product image word pairs)	15 neurons (15 EPV attributes)
NN1	Hidden layer	13 neurons, (20+6) / 2 = 13	18 neurons, (20+15) / 2 = 17.5 \doteq 18
NN2	Hidden layer	11 neurons, (20x6) ^ 0.5 = 10.95 \doteq 11	17 neurons, (20x15) ^ 0.5 = 17.32 \doteq 17
NN3	Hidden layer	26 neurons, (20+6) = 26	35 neurons, (20+15) = 35
NN4	Hidden layer	52 neurons, (20+6) x 2 =52	70 neurons, (20+15) x 2 = 70

Table 5. Neurons of four NN models.

Epochs	Product image word pair				EPV attribute			
	NN 1	NN 2	NN 3	NN 4	NN 1	NN 2	NN 3	NN 4
25000	0.1672*	0.1862	0.2533	0.4519	0.0928*	0.0997	0.2718	0.4835

Table 6. RMS error of four NN models for the test set for product image word pairs and EPV attributes.

multiattribute decision problems, in particular when the nature of the problem demands a systematic analysis, such as the complexity of the decision, regularity of the decision, and the significant consequences.

Based on the concept of the degree of optimality, the overall preference value of a design alternative is determined by its distance to the positive ideal solution and to the negative ideal solution. This concept has been implemented by a widely used MADM method called the technique for order preference by similarity to ideal solution (TOPSIS) (Yoon and Hwang, 1995, 1981; Deng et al., 2000) and has been applied widely under different decision contexts (e.g. Zeleny, 1998; Deng et al., 2000; Lin et al., 2008; Yeh and Chang, 2009).

The advantages of using this concept have been highlighted by (a) its intuitively appealing logic, (b) its simplicity and comprehensibility, (c) its computational efficiency, (d) its ability to measure the relative performance of the alternatives with respect to individual or all evaluation criteria in a simple mathematical form (Yeh and Chang, 2009). Hence, all design alternatives are compared with the positive and negative ideal solutions rather than directly among themselves.

In actual design settings, EPV attributes may be given different weights by designers, since there may be different degrees of importance for each EPV attribute in meeting specific design objectives. In this regard, a MADM approach can be used for determining the optimal value of eco-product form element combination with given weights of EPV attributes in the further analysis.

In the context of this study, 960 design alternatives ($j = 1, 2, \dots, 960$) are generated from the NN model while 15 EPV attributes ($j = 1, 2, \dots, 15$) are categorized into aesthetic, functional, and environment-friendly dimensions. The procedure of the TOPSIS technique can be expressed in the following six steps:

Step 1: Obtain normalized attribute weights of EPV attribute.

We interview 7 furniture design experts for giving weights to 3 EPV dimensions as z_k ($k = 1, 2, 3$) and their associated 15 attributes as w_j ($j = 1, 2, \dots, 15$), which is scaled from 1 to 9. The average weight for each attribute is generated and multiplied by its corresponding average weight as

$$Y_{kj} = \bar{z}_k \times \bar{w}_j \tag{1}$$

where $j = 1, 2, \dots, 7$ if $k = 1$
 $j = 8, 9, 10$ if $k = 2$
 $j = 11, 12, \dots, 15$ if $k = 3$

The normalized weight of the j th attribute is calculated as

$$w'_j = \frac{y_{1j}}{X} \quad j = 1; 2, \dots, 7$$

$$\frac{y_{2j}}{X} \quad j = 8, 9, 10$$

$$\frac{y_{3j}}{X} \quad j = 11, 12, \dots, 15 \tag{2}$$

where $X = \sum_{j=1}^7 Y_{1j} + \sum_{j=8}^{10} Y_{2j} + \sum_{j=11}^{15} Y_{3j}$;
 $\sum_{j=1}^{15} w'_j = 1.$

For example, the average weight (\bar{w}_1) for “Harmonious form proportion (Y_1)” (c_1) is 7.29 and “Aesthetics” dimension (z_1) is 7.57. The normalized weight (w'_1) is $7.29 \times 7.57 / 738.45 = 0.07$.

Normalized weights for Y_2 to Y_{15} are 0.07, 0.07, 0.06, 0.05, 0.06, 0.05, 0.08, 0.08, 0.05, 0.08, 0.06, 0.09, 0.07, and 0.07 respectively.

Step 2: Calculate the weighted normalized ratings. In this study, each attribute is measured on the same scale and the predicted rating is directly used. The weighted normalized value of r_{ij} , v_{ij} , can be calculated by

$$v_{ij} = w'_j r_{ij}, i = 1, 2, \dots, 960; j = 1, 2, \dots, 15 \quad (3)$$

A decision making matrix is established by multiplying weights by ratings.

Step 3: Determine the positive and negative ideal alternatives.

The ideal alternative is a hypothetical alternative in which all attribute values correspond to the best level. On the contrary, the negative ideal solution is also a hypothetical alternative in which all attribute values correspond to the worst level. The ideal alternative, A^+ , and the negative alternative, A^- are denote as

$$A^+ = \{ v_1^+, v_2^+, \dots, v_j^+, \dots, v_n^+, \} \\ = \{ (\max v_{ij} \mid j \in J_1), (\min v_{ij} \mid j \in J_2) \mid i = 1, 2, \dots, 960 \} \quad (4)$$

and

$$A^- = \{ v_1^-, v_2^-, \dots, v_j^-, \dots, v_n^-, \} \\ = \{ (\min v_{ij} \mid j \in J_1), (\max v_{ij} \mid j \in J_2) \mid i = 1, 2, \dots, 960 \} \quad (5)$$

where J_1 is a set of benefit attributes and J_2 is a set of cost attributes.

Since all the chosen attributes are of benefit (the higher, the more preference), the positive-ideal alternative consists of the largest value of each attribute. In this study, $A^+ = (0.286, 0.252, 0.306, 0.241, 0.185, 0.234, 0.202, 0.338, 0.337, 0.207,$

$0.285, 0.242, 0.395, 0.309, 0.255)$.

The smallest values of each attribute make the negative-ideal alternative. That is, $A^- = (0.116, 0.111, 0.108, 0.107, 0.095, 0.106, 0.105, 0.125, 0.126, 0.103, 0.181, 0.105, 0.179, 0.135, 0.155)$

Step 4: Calculate the separation measures.

The separation (distance) between alternatives can be measured by the n-dimensional Euclidean distance. The separation of each alternative from the ideal alternative, S_i^+ , is given as

$$S_i^+ = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^{15} (v_{ij} - v_j^*)^2}, i = 1, 2, \dots, 960 \quad (6)$$

Similarly, the separation from the negative alternative, S_i^- , is given as

$$S_i^- = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^{15} (v_{ij} - v_j^-)^2}, i = 1, 2, \dots, 960 \quad (7)$$

Step 5: Calculate the EPV value for each design alternative.

$$EPV_i^* = S_i^- / (S_i^+ + S_i^-), i = 1, 2, \dots, 960 \quad (8)$$

Clearly $EPV_i^* \in [0, 1]$, as $S_i^+ \geq 0$ and $S_i^- \geq 0$.

Step 6: Rank design alternatives by their EPV_i^* value for EPV attributes.

Five top ranked design alternatives with the EPV_i^* value for each armrest type are shown in Table 7.

DISCUSSION

In design objectives, product designers often face considerable challenges in the office chair design development process since there are various considerations with different degrees of importance. If the designers want to design an eco-product with high EPV attribute values and specific features, what should they do? If the designers want the eco-product to look more aesthetic, functional, and to

X_6 Armrest type	X_1 Back and seat	X_2 Back area	X_3 Back shape	X_4 Back thickness	X_5 Seat thickness	X_7 Base type	Total value (No.)
Loop (1)	Integrated (2)	Medium (2)	SRC (2)	Thin (2)	Thin (2)	5-wheel (1)	0.73 (711)
T-shaped (2)	Separated (1)	Medium (2)	SRC (2)	Thick (1)	Thin (2)	5-wheel (1)	0.70 (213)
2-point Support (3)	Integrated (2)	Large (1)	SRC (2)	Thin (2)	Thin (2)	5-wheel (1)	0.74 (555)
1-point Support (4)	Integrated (2)	Medium (2)	SRC (2)	Thin (2)	Thin (2)	5-wheel (1)	0.69 (717)
None (5)	Integrated (2)	Large (1)	SRC (2)	Thin (2)	Thin (2)	5-wheel (1)	0.80 (559)

Note: 1. SRC indicates Square with rounded corner. 2. No. indicates design alternative number in the database.

Table 7. Office chair form elements for the highest ranking on EPV attributes under each armrest type (X_6).

look very environment-friendly, what should they do? These questions can be answered by using the NN1 model developed. The NN1 model enables us to build an office chair design database that can be used to help determine the combination of office chair form elements for meeting specific office chair product image and EPV attribute values.

AN OFFICE CHAIR DESIGN DATABASE

The design database can be generated by inputting each of all possible combinations of product form elements to the NN1 model individually for generating the associated image values. The resultant eco-product design database consists of 960 (=2 × 3 × 4 × 2 × 2 × 5 × 2) different combinations of product form elements, together with their associated 6 product image values and 15 EPV attribute values.

The combinations of product form elements shown in Table 7 will produce the most aesthetic, functional, and environment-friendly office chairs for each armrest type as perceived by consumers. For example, office chair designers should consider using the “None” armrest type on office chairs in order to best match the consumers’ perception of very “aesthetic”, “functional”, and “environment-friendly” value attributes with the highest EPV attribute value 0.80.

APPLICATION FOR THE PRODUCT DESIGNER WITH SPECIFIC DESIGN OBJECTIVES

From the perspective of consumers, product designers may identify a particular design objective with specific product images for fitting consumers’ needs in addition to achieving a very high EPV

attribute value. Table 8 shows the value range for each product image word pair with 5 scales divided evenly based on the number of design alternatives. Table 9 shows the value range for the EPV with 5 scales divided evenly based on the number of design alternatives.

If the product designer wants to design an office chair which gives a specific design objective based on product image and EPV value, is there any restriction? What can the combination of product form elements be? To answer these questions, we establish the following steps:

1. The product designer can choose a specific product image which can indicate the respective value range. It is commonly agreed that “High” or “Very high” EPV attribute value should be chosen by product designers and consumers.
2. Based on the chosen product images and EPV attribute values at Step 1, product designers can review the 960 design alternatives in the office chair design database and choose design alternatives with both corresponded product image values and EPV attribute values.
3. Product designers can establish a general rule for the combination of office chair form elements (X_1 to X_7) for achieving specific design objective within the chosen value range of product images and EPV attributes at Step 2.

For example, there are 192 design alternatives with value less than 2.46 as the “Very classic” product image from the office chair design database. If the design objective is to design an office chair with both “Very classic” product image and “Very high” EPV attribute ($EPV \geq 0.60$), then there are only 22 design alternatives left for achieving this design

	Very	Moderate	Neutral	Moderate	Very	
Classic	C-M <2.46	2.46 ≤ C-M <3.21	3.21 ≤ C-M <3.77	3.77 ≤ C-M <4.23	4.23 ≤ C-M	Modern
Decorative	D-F <2.06	2.06 ≤ D-F <2.75	2.75 ≤ D-F <3.30	3.30 ≤ D-F <3.78	3.78 ≤ D-F	Functional
Angular	A-R <2.09	2.09 ≤ A-R <2.71	2.71 ≤ A-R <3.26	3.26 ≤ A-R <3.96	3.96 ≤ A-R	Round
Heavy	H-L <2.47	2.47 ≤ H-L <3.09	3.09 ≤ H-L <3.53	3.53 ≤ H-L <4.06	4.06 ≤ H-L	Light
Craft	C-H <2.14	2.14 ≤ C-H <2.60	2.60 ≤ C-H <3.06	3.06 ≤ C-H <3.47	3.47 ≤ C-H	HiTech
Monotonous	M-C <2.12	2.12 ≤ M-C <2.64	2.64 ≤ M-C <3.19	3.19 ≤ M-C <3.75	3.75 ≤ M-C	Creative

Table 8. Value range for each product image word pair

Very low	Low	Moderate	High	Very high
EPV <0.46	0.46 ≤ EPV <0.50	0.50 ≤ EPV <0.55	0.55 ≤ EPV <0.60	0.60 ≤ EPV

Table 9. Value range of the EPV

No.	X ₁ Back and seat	X ₂ Back area	X ₃ Back shape	X ₄ Back thickness	X ₅ Seat thickness	X ₆ Armrest type	X ₇ Base type
1	Integrated (X ₁₂)	Medium (X ₂₂)	SRC (X ₃₂)	Thick (X ₄₁)	Thin (X ₅₂)	None (X ₆₅)	5-wheel (X ₇₁)
2	Integrated (X ₁₂)	Medium (X ₂₂)	SRC (X ₃₂)	Thick (X ₄₁)	Thin (X ₅₂)	T-shaped (X ₆₂)	5-wheel (X ₇₁)
3	Integrated (X ₁₂)	Medium (X ₂₂)	SRC (X ₃₂)	Thick (X ₄₁)	Thin (X ₅₂)	2-point support (X ₆₃)	5-wheel (X ₇₁)
4	Integrated (X ₁₂)	Large (X ₂₁)	SRC (X ₃₂)	Thick (X ₄₁)	Thin (X ₅₂)	None (X ₆₅)	5-wheel (X ₇₁)
5	Integrated (X ₁₂)	Large (X ₂₁)	SRC (X ₃₂)	Thick (X ₄₁)	Thin (X ₅₂)	T-shaped (X ₆₂)	5-wheel (X ₇₁)
6	Integrated (X ₁₂)	Large (X ₂₁)	SRC (X ₃₂)	Thick (X ₄₁)	Thin (X ₅₂)	2-point support (X ₆₃)	5-wheel (X ₇₁)

Note: 1. SRC indicates Square with rounded corner. 2. No. indicates design alternative number.

Table 10. Product form element combination for designing office chairs for “Very classic” product image and “Very high” EPV office chairs

Figure 2. A 3D design sketch for achieving the design objective of “Very classic” and “Very high” EPV based on design alternative 3 in Table 10

objective. The general rule with six product form element combinations for the “Very classic” and “Very high” EPV office chair design is established, as shown in Table 10. Thus, product designers can choose one of the design alternatives according to specific design requirements while meeting the design objective. In other words, if product designers want to design an office chair based on design alternative 3, the form elements should be the Back and seat (X₁) being “Integrated (X₁₂)”, Back area (X₂) being “Medium(X₂₂)”, Back shape (X₃) being “Square with rounded corner (X₃₂)”, Back thickness (X₄) being “Thick (X₄₁)”, Seat thickness (X₅) being “Thin (X₅₂)”, Armrest type (X₆) being “2-point support (X₆₃)”, and the Base type (X₇) being “5-wheel (X₇₁)”. Figure 2

shows an example of the design sketch based on design alternative 3 in Table 10.

CONCLUSION

This paper studies for the first time the trade-offs the product designer may face when making eco-product design decisions with the value concept of eco-products. The eco-product value (EPV) categorized into aesthetic, functional, and environmental dimensions can be adopted to reflect a variety of different considerations. The consumer-oriented value evaluation approach developed in this study is novel in that the target eco-product design parameter is the consumer perceived EPV, which is different from existing techniques for eco-product design and evaluation. The results of this paper have justified the approach by carrying out eco-product value evaluation for the combination of office chair form elements.

Using the office chair design database developed in this study, the combination of form elements, product image values, and EPV attribute values can be set up to be used for specific design objectives. As such, the database can help product designers select the best combination of office chair form elements for meeting specific design objectives based on product image values and EPV attribute

values. Although the product form is chosen as an illustration of the approach, the approach can be applied to other design elements such as colour and texture of eco-products. Further research can be carried out on ways to derive EPV attribute variables and to establish an EPV indicator.

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